

XUSUSIY HOSILALI DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALARNI
MATLAB DASTURI YORDAMIDA YECHISH

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<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8194894>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 20th July 2023

Accepted: 28th July 2023

Online: 29th July 2023

KEY WORDS

Matlab dasturi, kross-diffuziya,
tizim, avtomodel, yechim,
nodivergent, blow-up.

ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada Giperbolik turdagi xususiy hosilali differensial tenglamalarni matlab dasturi yordamida echilish qoidalari ko'rsatib berilgan.

Giperbolik turdagi xususiy hosilali differensial tenglamalarni matlab dasturi yordamida echilishini ko'rib chiqamiz. Quyidagi misolni qaraymiz:

Misol: $G = \{0 < x < 1, 0 < t < 1\}$ sohada

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}$$

to'r tenglamasining

$$u(0, t) = u(1, t) = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$u(x, 0) = \sin \pi x, \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial t}(x, 0) = 0 \quad (2)$$

chegaraviy va dastlabki shartlarni qanoqlantiradigan taqribiy echimi topilsin.

Yechish: Bu masalani to'r metodi yordanida echamiz. Bu erda h va l qadamlarni o'zimiz misol tanlab olamiz. Demak $h=0.04$, $l=0.05$ bo'lsin. Matlab dasturi yordamida qadamlarni va shu qadamdagi tugunlar qiymatlarini hisoblaymiz.

Biz yuqorida quyidagicha to'r kiritgan edik:

$$G_{hl} = \{x_i = ih, i = 0, \overline{M}, hM = 1; t_k = kl, k = 0, \overline{N}, Nl = T\} \quad (3)$$

Demak (3) ga asosan m va n lar quyidagicha:

$$m = \frac{1}{h}, n = \frac{T}{l}$$

Misol shartiga ko'ra $T=1$ bo'ladi.


```
MATLAB R2012a
File Edit Debug Parallel Desktop Window Help
Shortcuts How to Add What's New
New to MATLAB? Watch this Video, see Demos, or read Getting Started.
>> h=input('x ning qadami h ni kiriting. h=');
x ning qadami h ni kiriting. h=0.04;
>> l=input('t ning qadami h ni kiriting. l=');
t ning qadami h ni kiriting. l=0.05;
>> T=input('T=');
T=1;
>> m=1/h;
>> n=T/l;
fx >> |
```

1.rasm

Bu erdan n va m ning qiymatlariga ega bo'lamiz: Bu quyida ko'rsatilgan.
Workspace bo'limiga kiramiz.

Name	Value	Min	Max
T	1	1	1
h	0.0400	0.0400	0.0400
l	0.0500	0.0500	0.0500
m	25	25	25
n	20	20	20

2.rasm

Yana (3) dan foydalaning va tugunlarning qiymatlari x_i va t_k larni quyidagicha topamiz:

$$x_i = ih, i = \overline{0, M}, hM = 1; t_k = kl, k = \overline{0, N}, Nl = T$$

```
MATLAB R2012a
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>> h=input('x ning qadami h ni kiriting. h=');
x ning qadami h ni kiriting. h=0.04;
>> l=input('t ning qadami h ni kiriting. l=');
t ning qadami h ni kiriting. l=0.05;
>> T=input('T=');
T=1;
>> m=1/h;
>> n=T/l;
>> for i=1:m+1
x(i)=(i-1)*h;
end;
>> for k=1:n+1
t(k)=(k-1)*l;
end;
fx >>
```

3.rasm

Izoh: Matlab dasturida massiv elementlari birinchi elementdan boshlanadi. Ya'ni $x(0) = i * h$ desak dastur ishlamaydi shuning uchun $x(0)$ o'rniga $x(1)$ tanlanadi ya'ni bir qadam siljiriladi. Demak x_i va t_k larning qiymatlariga ega bo'ldik.

Endi (2) dastlabki shartdan foydalanib y_{i0} va y_{i1} larni topamiz. Demak $y_{i0} = \phi(x_i), y_{i1} = \phi(x_i) + l\psi(x_i) + \frac{l^2}{2} \Delta_2\phi_i$ bo'ladi. Bunda

$\Delta_2\phi_i = \frac{1}{h^2}(\phi(x_{i+1}) - 2\phi(x_i) + \phi(x_{i-1}))$ edi. Boshlang'ich shartga ko'ra

$\phi(x) = \sin(\pi x), \psi(x) = 0$ bo'ladi.

Bu erda $f(x) = \phi(x), ff(x) = \psi(x)$ belgilashlar olingan.

```

Command Window
New to MATLAB? Watch this Video, see Demos, or read Getting Started.
>> h=input('x ning qadami h ni kiriting. h=');
x ning qadami h ni kiriting. h=0.04;
>> l=input('t ning qadami h ni kiriting. l=');
t ning qadami h ni kiriting. l=0.05;
>> T=input('T=');
T=1;
>> m=1/h;
>> n=T/l;
>> for i=1:m+1
x(i)=(i-1)*h;
end;
>> for k=1:n+1
t(k)=(k-1)*l;
end;
>> for i=1:m+1
f(i)=sin(pi*(i-1));
end;
>> for i=1:m+1
ff(i)=0;
end;
>> for i=2:m
y(i,1)=f(i);
end;
>> for i=2:m
y(i,2)=f(i)+l*ff(i)+(l*l/(2*h*h))*(f(i+1)-2*f(i)+f(i-1));
end;
fx
    
```

4.rasm

Endi (1) chegaraviy shartdan foydalanib $y_{0,k+1}$ va $y_{m,k+1}$ larni topamiz. Buning uchun quydagi formuladan foydalanamiz.

$$y_{0,k+1} = \mu_1(t_{k+1}), y_{m,k+1} = \mu_2(t_{k+1}), k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 1N - 1.$$

Chegaraviy shartga ko'ra $\mu_1(t) = 0, \mu_2(t) = 0$ bo'ladi.

Qulaylik uchun $myu = \mu_1(t) = \mu_2(t) = 0$ belgilash kiritamiz.


```
Command Window
New to MATLAB? Watch this Video, see Demos, or read Getting Started.

>> for i=1:m+1
x(i)=(i-1)*h;
end;
>> for k=1:n+1
t(k)=(k-1)*l;
end;
>> for i=1:m+1
f(i)=sin(pi*(i-1));
end;
>> for i=1:m+1
ff(i)=0;
end;
>> for i=2:m
y(i,1)=f(i);
end;
>> for i=2:m
y(i,2)=f(i)+l*ff(i)+(l*l/(2*h*h))*(f(i+1)-2*f(i)+f(i-1));
end;
>> myu=0;
>> for k=1:n
y(1,k+1)=myu;
end;
>> for k=1:n
y(m+1,k+1)=myu;
end;
fx >>
```

5.rasm

Endi qolgan tugindagi qiymatlarni hisoblaymiz.

$$y_{i,k+1} = 2y_{ik} + l^2 \Delta_2 y_{ik} - y_{i,k-1}, i = 1, 2, \dots, M - 1$$

Bu erda $\Delta_2 y_{ik} = \frac{1}{h^2} (y_{i+1,k} - 2y_{ik} + y_{i-1,k})$ bo'ladi.

```
Command Window
New to MATLAB? Watch this Video, see Demos, or read Getting Started.

end;
>> for i=1:m+1
f(i)=sin(pi*(i-1));
end;
>> for i=1:m+1
ff(i)=0;
end;
>> for i=2:m
y(i,1)=f(i);
end;
>> for i=2:m
y(i,2)=f(i)+l*ff(i)+(l*l/(2*h*h))*(f(i+1)-2*f(i)+f(i-1));
end;
>> myu=0;
>> for k=1:n
y(1,k+1)=myu;
end;
>> for k=1:n
y(m+1,k+1)=myu;
end;
>> for i=2:m
for k=2:n
y(i,k+1)=2*y(i,k)+(l*l/(h*h))*(y(i+1,k)-2*y(i,k)+y(i-1,k))-y(i,k-1);
end;
end;
fx >>
```

6.rasm

Demak natijani *Workspake* bo'limidan olamiz.

Name	Value	Min	Max
T	1	1	1
f	<1x26 double>	-9.799...	6.3694...
ff	<1x26 double>	0	0
h	0.0400	0.0400	0.0400
i	25	25	25
k	20	20	20
l	0.0500	0.0500	0.0500
m	25	25	25
myu	0	0	0
n	20	20	20
t	<1x21 double>	0	1
x	<1x26 double>	0	1
y	<26x21 double>	-3.161...	2.6512...

7.rasm

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	1.2246e-16	-2.6024e-16	9.8354e-16	-8.4625e-16	-3.1513e-17	8.8170e-16	-9.6040e-16	1.9875e-16	7.3681e-16	-1.0277e-15	4.1931e-16
3	-2.4493e-16	5.2047e-16	-1.9671e-15	3.2293e-15	-2.9881e-15	8.3114e-17	4.2723e-15	-6.3901e-15	3.2271e-15	3.9109e-15	-9.2325e-15
4	3.6739e-16	-7.8071e-16	2.9506e-15	-5.6123e-15	8.4090e-15	-8.5167e-15	1.3022e-15	1.3727e-14	-2.6730e-14	2.1386e-14	8.7811e-15
5	-4.8986e-16	1.0409e-15	-3.9342e-15	7.9954e-15	-1.3830e-14	2.0702e-14	-2.2768e-14	6.9460e-15	3.6402e-14	-8.9664e-14	9.7885e-14
6	6.1232e-16	-1.3012e-15	4.9177e-15	-1.0378e-14	1.9251e-14	-3.2888e-14	5.0095e-14	-5.9044e-14	2.7182e-14	8.5342e-14	-2.6329e-13
7	-7.3479e-16	1.5614e-15	-5.9013e-15	1.2761e-14	-2.4672e-14	4.5073e-14	-7.7423e-14	1.2030e-13	-1.5017e-13	9.1114e-14	1.8102e-13
8	8.5725e-16	-1.8217e-15	6.8848e-15	-1.5144e-14	3.0092e-14	-5.7259e-14	1.0475e-13	-1.8156e-13	2.8748e-13	-3.7649e-13	2.7845e-13
9	-9.7972e-16	2.0819e-15	-7.8684e-15	1.7528e-14	-3.5513e-14	6.9445e-14	-1.3208e-13	2.4282e-13	-4.2478e-13	6.8424e-13	-9.3326e-13
10	1.1022e-15	-2.3421e-15	1.3189e-14	-2.4789e-14	4.2086e-14	-7.8047e-14	1.5422e-13	-3.0183e-13	5.6474e-13	-9.9721e-13	1.6263e-12
11	-1.2246e-15	5.3779e-15	-1.6080e-14	3.3320e-14	-6.0138e-14	1.0010e-13	-1.7442e-13	3.3710e-13	-6.7643e-13	1.3063e-12	-2.3513e-12
12	4.8998e-15	-4.8610e-15	1.3851e-14	-3.5847e-14	7.8539e-14	-1.4648e-13	2.4264e-13	-3.9903e-13	7.3298e-13	-1.4825e-12	2.9759e-12
13	-1.4696e-15	3.1228e-15	-1.1803e-14	3.1798e-14	-7.9981e-14	1.8090e-13	-3.5240e-13	5.9468e-13	-9.4009e-13	1.6082e-12	-3.1855e-12
14	-1.9607e-15	-1.3847e-15	1.4091e-14	-3.2909e-14	7.2615e-14	-1.7375e-13	4.0551e-13	-8.3307e-13	1.4609e-12	-2.2793e-12	3.6162e-12
15	-1.7145e-15	3.6433e-15	-1.3770e-14	3.3864e-14	-7.5747e-14	1.6481e-13	-3.8116e-13	8.9761e-13	-1.9303e-12	3.5566e-12	-5.6323e-12
16	5.3897e-15	-5.9020e-15	1.3449e-14	-3.0743e-14	7.4050e-14	-1.7092e-13	3.7575e-13	-8.4737e-13	1.9800e-12	-4.3963e-12	8.5230e-12
17	-1.9594e-15	4.1638e-15	-1.5737e-14	3.4554e-14	-7.1172e-14	1.6122e-13	-3.7726e-13	8.5031e-13	-1.9034e-12	4.3848e-12	-9.8987e-12
18	-1.4708e-15	-2.4256e-15	1.8025e-14	-4.2441e-14	8.3711e-14	-1.6294e-13	3.5150e-13	-8.2196e-13	1.9018e-12	-4.2916e-12	9.7774e-12
19	-2.2044e-15	4.6843e-15	-1.7704e-14	4.3396e-14	-9.7431e-14	1.9701e-13	-3.7880e-13	7.7835e-13	-1.7812e-12	4.1970e-12	-9.6461e-12
20	5.8795e-15	-6.9429e-15	1.7383e-14	-4.0275e-14	9.5733e-14	-2.1966e-13	4.5922e-13	-8.8883e-13	1.7569e-12	-3.8707e-12	9.1556e-12
21	-2.4493e-15	5.2047e-15	-2.8345e-14	5.3843e-14	-9.5159e-14	2.0279e-13	-4.7620e-13	1.0505e-12	-2.0944e-12	4.0509e-12	-8.5109e-12
22	-9.8096e-16	-9.0177e-15	3.4449e-14	-7.4026e-14	1.3296e-13	-2.2424e-13	4.3618e-13	-1.0105e-12	2.3420e-12	-4.8967e-12	9.4962e-12
23	-9.7997e-15	9.7220e-15	-3.6376e-14	8.5028e-14	-1.7495e-13	3.1954e-13	-5.3491e-13	9.6376e-13	-2.1283e-12	5.0899e-12	-1.1249e-11
24	6.3694e-15	-1.3535e-14	3.3807e-14	-8.1336e-14	1.9055e-13	-4.0639e-13	7.6591e-13	-1.2911e-12	2.1924e-12	-4.5008e-12	1.0824e-11
25	-2.9392e-15	6.2457e-15	-2.5236e-14	7.4968e-14	-1.8619e-13	4.3223e-13	-9.3505e-13	1.8164e-12	-3.1257e-12	5.1256e-12	-9.6731e-12
26	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
27											

8.rasm

	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	5.5594e-16	-1.0447e-15	6.1939e-16	3.4792e-16	-1.0108e-15	7.8923e-16	1.2292e-16	-9.2751e-16	9.2054e-16	-1.0809e-16
3	7.1309e-15	2.0789e-15	-1.1102e-14	1.1379e-14	-1.1554e-15	-1.1658e-14	1.5504e-14	-5.5918e-15	-1.0663e-14	1.9026e-14
4	-4.5691e-14	5.3763e-14	-1.1544e-14	-5.8123e-14	9.4711e-14	-5.0233e-14	-5.6415e-14	1.3793e-13	-1.0749e-13	-3.3662e-14
5	-6.7368e-15	-1.6170e-13	2.7265e-13	-1.6307e-13	-1.8001e-13	5.1357e-13	-4.7625e-13	-6.5944e-14	7.6594e-13	-9.6369e-13
6	3.6381e-13	-1.5652e-13	-4.4038e-13	1.0780e-12	-1.0271e-12	-2.0371e-13	2.0588e-12	-2.8565e-12	1.0518e-12	2.8700e-12
7	-7.0615e-13	1.1819e-12	-8.6799e-13	-8.9346e-13	3.5574e-12	-4.7136e-12	1.4270e-12	6.3250e-12	-1.3006e-11	9.9501e-12
8	3.4608e-13	-1.7711e-12	3.4931e-12	-3.5148e-12	-9.3495e-13	1.0125e-11	-1.7821e-11	1.2153e-11	1.4031e-11	-4.8260e-11
9	8.0076e-13	5.7316e-13	-4.2130e-12	9.6244e-12	-1.2106e-11	2.5344e-12	2.5076e-11	-5.8590e-11	5.9826e-11	1.3209e-11
10	-2.2905e-12	2.2018e-12	7.0910e-13	-9.5823e-12	2.5109e-11	-3.7582e-11	2.1130e-11	5.2991e-11	-1.7229e-10	2.3432e-10
11	3.8799e-12	-5.5926e-12	5.8520e-12	1.1703e-13	-2.0956e-11	6.2692e-11	-1.0829e-10	9.2155e-11	8.7418e-11	-4.5970e-10
12	-5.5393e-12	9.3182e-12	-1.3682e-11	1.5218e-11	-3.2553e-12	-4.4300e-11	1.5105e-10	-2.9484e-10	3.2464e-10	6.6212e-10
13	6.6253e-12	-1.2923e-11	2.2473e-11	-3.3737e-11	3.9260e-11	-1.5516e-11	-9.1022e-11	3.5393e-10	-7.6783e-10	1.0171e-09
14	-6.7663e-12	1.4348e-11	-2.9567e-11	5.4029e-11	-8.3930e-11	1.0174e-10	-5.4767e-11	-1.8234e-10	8.1292e-10	-1.9319e-09
15	8.4300e-12	-1.4424e-11	3.0215e-11	-6.5768e-11	1.2819e-10	-2.0959e-10	2.6656e-10	-1.7586e-10	-3.5363e-10	1.8439e-09
16	-1.3993e-11	2.0390e-11	-3.1484e-11	6.2240e-11	-1.4130e-10	2.9702e-10	-5.2034e-10	7.0485e-10	-5.4740e-10	-6.4157e-10
17	2.0069e-11	-3.4542e-11	5.0651e-11	-7.1634e-11	1.2719e-10	-2.9223e-10	6.6567e-10	-1.2697e-09	1.8640e-09	-1.6827e-09
18	-2.2175e-11	4.6526e-11	-8.4139e-11	1.2727e-10	-1.7097e-10	2.6380e-10	-5.8242e-10	1.4315e-09	-3.0119e-09	4.8695e-09
19	2.1932e-11	-4.9676e-11	1.0665e-10	-2.0177e-10	3.1921e-10	-4.2448e-10	5.7052e-10	-1.1274e-09	2.9346e-09	-6.8801e-09
20	-2.1501e-11	4.9302e-11	-1.1158e-10	2.4287e-10	-4.7692e-10	7.9242e-10	-1.0778e-09	1.3115e-09	-2.1592e-09	5.7028e-09
21	1.9829e-11	-4.7393e-11	1.1052e-10	-2.5129e-10	5.5166e-10	-1.1145e-09	1.9403e-09	-2.7524e-09	3.2054e-09	-4.2275e-09
22	-1.9085e-11	4.2958e-11	-1.0329e-10	2.4594e-10	-5.6603e-10	1.2528e-09	-2.5848e-09	4.6868e-09	-6.9885e-09	8.1838e-09
23	2.2403e-11	-4.3775e-11	9.3965e-11	-2.2333e-10	5.4157e-10	-1.2704e-09	2.8451e-09	-5.9692e-09	1.1193e-08	-1.7543e-08
24	-2.5253e-11	5.2590e-11	-1.0231e-10	2.0933e-10	-4.8214e-10	1.1793e-09	-2.8295e-09	6.4494e-09	-1.3753e-08	2.6512e-08
25	2.2669e-11	-5.5287e-11	1.2170e-10	-2.4148e-10	4.7704e-10	-1.0485e-09	2.5452e-09	-6.2358e-09	1.4547e-08	-3.1619e-08
26	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
27										

9.rasm

Olingan jadvaldan ko'rinib turibdi x_i ning qiymatlari ustun shaklida t_k ning qiymatlari satr shaklida joylashgan.

10-rasm

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